

FIDELIS TTRAMatrix (v01.00) Guide (v01.00)

Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

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Scope

Through the TTRAM (Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix) the FIDELIS Network examines 30 common repository activities and functions in groups: digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security.¹ Each activity or function is considered against local repository variables:

1. the levels of retention, curation and preservation provided by the repository
2. the characteristics of the repositories' digital objects, depositors and users

Together, these activities, functions and local variables are used to propose related information (including policies, standards and procedures) that could usefully be made transparent.

Repositories can immediately benefit by using the TTRAM as a reference point for examining priority activities or functions, or by using the full list of activities and functions as a planning and implementation checklist.

The greater benefit of the TTRAM will be realised as the FIDELIS project, and future Network, use it as a baseline for work including classification of existing resources, mapping to criteria, standards and requirements and in developing guidance for information transparency.

In this way the TTRAM will provide a flexible, evolving tool to support mutual understanding, support and alignment within and beyond the FIDELIS Network.

The TTRAM is *not* an assessment, test, or FIDELIS Network application form. It does not have to be 'completed' and there are no 'wrong answers'.

This document provides a brief guide to the TTRAM and the related materials.

All comments are welcome via email: fidelis.matrixfeedback-request@postit.csc.fi.

¹ Information on the FIDELIS Network can be found at: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/our-networks>

Introduction

Understanding the range of repositories and other potential stakeholders in the future FIDELIS Network is essential. This brief guide is intended to provide enough information for repositories, standards developers and policy makers to consider how their work aligns with the evolving Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM).

An [Introduction and Overview](#) paper² provides more detail on how the Matrix can be deployed, populated and expanded. The parameters and drivers behind the selection of the activities and functions (A|F), levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) and the digital object, depositor and user characteristics supported by different repository types are covered in a separate [Design Statement](#).³

The Matrix is presented as a [template spreadsheet](#)⁴ with examples and suggestions. The full text is also included in this Guide.

The TTRAM is *not* an assessment, test, or FIDELIS Network application form. It does not have to be 'completed' and there are no 'wrong answers'.

The Matrix is divided into list of common activities or functions (A|F) based on a range of existing standards, criteria and requirements.⁵ Transparency of information is a dependency for mutual understanding, cooperation and support, so the Matrix suggests and collects information (policies, procedures, metadata etc) about repositories' practices.

Transparency does not necessarily imply that information must always be public. The degree of transparency required depends on the context. Some criteria might prefer that supporting information is made public (e.g. CoreTrustSeal certification evidence⁶), while other contexts, such as cooperation between repositories and suppliers, or within a working group, may permit more limited transparency.

² TTRAM Introduction and Overview: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676337>

³ TTRAM Design Statement <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15677075>

⁴ TTRAM template spreadsheet: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676331>

⁵ Metadata and Data Services Activities-Functions: Crosswalk <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7690657>

⁶ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements 2023-2025: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

The specific information to be shared about each A|F is influenced by repository variables. These focus on the levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) provided by the repository, and the scope of its objects, depositors and users. Details are provided in the [Variables](#) section below.

Repositories can immediately benefit by using the TTRAM as a reference point for:

- examining priority activities or functions with a view to greater understanding, transparency and improvement
- using the activities, functions and associated information as a checklist for considering a particular repository target or goal.

The greater benefit of the TTRAM will be realised as the FIDELIS project uses it as a baseline for future work. FIDELIS will validate and publish mappings between the A|F and existing criteria to support Network members in managing alignment with different expectations. FIDELIS will also explore additional variables that influence local repository practice and transparency. Existing and newly developed FIDELIS support and training resources will be classified and categorised using the TTRAM to support their discovery, use and maintenance. In addition, the TTRAM will be aligned with the EDEN Core Preservation Processes⁷.

The TTRAM development has proceeded iteratively, informed by community feedback. The process is described in the milestone report [FIDELIS MS12 First Version of TTRAM](#)⁸.

⁷ EOSC EDEN T1.2, Lindlar, M., Caron, B., Benauer, M., Kylander, J., Dekeyser, K., Addis, M., Levlin, M., Laukkanen, M., Lehtonen, J., Burger, F., Koho, T., Schwab, F., Molloy, L., & Zhang, F. (2025). M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452>

⁸ FIDELIS MS12 First version of TTRAM (2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17157958>

Structure of the TTRAM

Activities & Functions

Activities & Functions of the TTRAM

Common repository Activities and Functions (A|F) are grouped by Digital Object Management, Organisational Infrastructure, Technology and Security. Each is supported by a brief description. See example below.

Group	Activity/ Function (A F)	Description
Digital Object Management	Deposit & Appraisal	Accepting custody of digital objects from depositors, transferring responsibility to the repository. It may also include appraising offered or requested deposits to ensure they meet established criteria for acceptance.

Transparent Information

The FIDELIS TTRAM spreadsheet template provides space for adding titles, descriptions and links to information artefacts (policies, procedures, references, standards, legislation etc), and metadata relevant to the A|F. Examples and suggestions in the template can be included, amended or deleted as necessary. See example below.

Transparent Information
<p>Documentation of compliance criteria applied at the point of deposits, whether automated or manually applied and the degree to which they are required or optional.</p> <p>Collections Development and Appraisal Policy</p> <p>Deposit Compliance Criteria</p> <p>Deposit Procedures</p> <p>Deposit Licence</p> <p>Acceptable/Preferred File Formats List</p>

Variables

Each activity or function is considered against local repository variables. The current variables included in the TTRAM are:

- the levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) provided by the repository
- the characteristics of the repository's digital objects, depositors and users

The template provides space to note how the local repository variables influence an A|F and the associated information.

If a variable influences an A|F then this is either stated or examples are provided. If a variable is not applicable (N/A) to an A|F, then this is stated. Examples and suggestions in the template can be included, amended or deleted as necessary.

Variables	
Levels of Retention, Curation & Preservation (LoRCAP)	Repository Depositors, Users and Objects (Included / Excluded)
LoRCAP: maps to Deposit Criteria. Depending on the LoRCAP deposit of an object may be permitted or restricted based on suitability for initial curation or active preservation.	Institutional repositories may limit depositors to one or more specific organisations. National repositories may require that research or a researcher is based in a specific country or that the digital object is relevant to users in a specific nation. Specialist repositories may permit or restrict objects based on their disciplinary relevance, supporting metadata, content types or funders.

Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)

Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)

The selected levels of care were produced through a CoreTrustSeal community consultation⁹, endorsed by the EOSC Long Term Data Preservation Task Force¹⁰, and will be referenced by the ongoing EOSC Retention Task Force¹¹.

⁹CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

¹⁰ EOSC Long Term Data Preservation Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

¹¹ EOSC Retention Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

Levels of retention, curation and preservation can influence what information is made transparent about each A|F.

Z. Level Zero. Retention-only

Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access. Data content and supporting metadata are stored for a given time period.

D. Deposit Compliance

Data content and supporting metadata deposited are checked for compliance with defined criteria.

C. Initial Curation

The digital objects are curated by the repository to meet defined criteria.

A. Active Preservation

Long-term responsibility for ensuring that the data and metadata can be understood and rendered as required by the designated community for reuse.

Repository Depositors, Users and Objects

Commonly referred to repository types include:

- Institutional
- Regional, National, International
- Generalist
- Disciplinary/Domain/Specialist

However, these traditional repository labels have limitations. Restrictions on the scope of depositors, collections and users in different repository types will influence whether a researcher should or could select them for their research outputs. This variable focuses on characteristics that cause objects, depositors or users to be included or excluded from the repository collection and/or services:

- Depositors accepted/rejected e.g. based on institutional affiliation.
- Users accepted/rejected e.g. based on geographic location.
- Digital objects types and content accepted/rejected for deposit, curation, preservation and access.

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This section begins by addressing local repository context including mission and scope, and then groups each Activity or Function (A|F) of the TTRAM by Digital Object Management, Organisational Infrastructure, Technology and Security.

Context

Both AF01 and AF02 are delivered via 'Organisational Infrastructure' but are presented separately here as they provide essential context across all Activities and Functions.

AF01 Identification & Contact

Names, abbreviations and contact details for the organisation to provide reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

- Organisation Name
- Organisation Alternative Names
- Organisation Identifier(s)
- Catalogue identifiers and locations
- Contact details

Variable Notes:

Not Applicable (N/A)

AF02 Mission & Scope

Defining the purpose (or mission) of the organisation and the boundaries of activities for which the repository is responsible. Where activities involve partners or outsourced services, the organisation retains ultimate responsibility for the activities, functions and outcomes.

Provides reference information and context for the rest of the activities and functions.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

- Organisation Mission Statement
- The LoRCAP offered by the repository
- Repository Type
- Designated Community
- Permitted/Restricted Object, Depositor and User Characteristics
- Geographic and linguistic coverage
- Whether a repository is FAIR-enabling or endorses the TRUST or CARE Principles

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: range of LoRCAP offered by repository.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Repository mission and scope define the range of objects to be collected and the characteristics of the depositors and users to be served.

Digital Object Management

Digital Object Management

AF03 Conceive, Create, Collect

The stages of the research data lifecycle, before data enters a repository. Working with data or metadata creators and owners can help improve quality and highlight the benefits of curation, preservation and reuse.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Any information or guidance provided to researchers about how to manage their digital objects' data and metadata during the pre-repository phase.

- Funding Information
- Project Information
- Data Management Plan (DMP)

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Any depositor, user or object permissions/restrictions may guide where a repository engages in this pre-repository phase.

AF04 Deposit & Appraisal

Accepting custody of digital objects from depositors, transferring responsibility to the repository. It may also include appraising offered or requested deposits to ensure they meet established criteria for acceptance.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Documentation of compliance criteria applied at the point of deposits, whether automated or manually applied and the degree to which they are required or optional.

- Collections Development and Appraisal Policy
- Deposit Compliance Criteria
- Deposit Procedures
- Acceptable/Preferred File Formats List
- ReAppraisal Plan, Data Management Plan
- Deposit licence (see also AF15 "Rights")

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: maps to Deposit Criteria

Depending on the LoRCAP deposit of an object may be permitted or restricted based on suitability for initial curation or active preservation.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Institutional repositories may limit depositors to one or more specific organisations. National repositories may require that research or a researcher is based in a specific country or that the digital object is relevant to users in a specific nation. Specialist repositories may permit or restrict objects based on their disciplinary relevance, supporting metadata, content types or funders.

AF05 Curation, Quality & Compliance

Ensuring digital objects reach a defined level of quality and standards compliance before they are made available for reuse.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Documentation of any initial curation steps taken after deposit to meet defined criteria for access and reuse and potentially to enable preservation, including any curation steps like conversions to file formats and any additions to metadata.

- Quality and Standards statements

- Standard operating procedures (SoP, Quality criteria)
- Compliance and Quality assurance policies and procedures

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: maps to Initial Curation

Not relevant to retention-only or deposit compliance repositories that don't undertake curation. Depending on the LoRCAP, initial curation may also include preparation for Active Preservation.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Specialist repositories need specific skills in data formats, research methodologies, metadata, and ontologies related to disciplines or content types.

AF06 Discovery & Identification

Applying persistent identifiers and descriptive metadata to digital objects to support resource discovery. Providing discovery systems and making metadata available for harvesting.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Persistent identifiers used (ideally chosen from a controlled vocabulary) for objects, organisations, researchers, software etc, and information about whether all objects are persistently identified. Information about identification at a more granular level (files within objects, questions within surveys, variables within statistics). Links to resource discovery systems that the repository provides or third parties that index metadata harvested from the repository collection.

- Persistent Identifier system(s)
- PID Policy
- Discovery metadata and documentation
- Resource discovery catalogues
- Harvesting protocols (e.g. OAI-PMH)

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: N/A

Depositors, Users, Objects: Specialist repositories use specific metadata and ontologies related to disciplines or content types for resource discovery.

AF07 Access

Determining the appropriate method of access—such as direct download or use within a secure remote environment—and facilitating user access accordingly. Access criteria are based on the characteristics of both the digital objects and the users, in alignment with rights management policies (see AF15 "Rights").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

- Access routes & methods,
- Access Management Policy
- Documentation of access routes and methods, including machine harvesting
- Licence and terms of access (see also AF15 "Rights")

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: N/A

Depositors, Users, Objects: Institutional repositories may limit users to one or more specific organisations. National repositories may require that users are based in, or that data are about a specific country. Sensitive digital objects may not be openly accessible, user access may depend on their qualifications or training.

AF08 ReUse

Making and keeping digital objects usable and understandable depends on deposit, curation, and preservation activities. Facilitating reuse depends on understanding the needs and expectations of users, including—but not limited to—identified 'designated communities', through ongoing external engagement (see AF20 "External Engagement"). Repositories may mediate reuse through secure remote access systems, safe rooms, or other tools that keep the digital objects fully or partially under the service provider's control.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

References to artefacts including file formats, metadata and ontologies (potentially already mentioned under Deposit or Curation) that are specifically designed to enable reuse. Designated Community definitions, digital object models.

- Terms and Conditions for Use
- Designated Community Consultation information

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: Some repositories and data services, e.g. retention-only, may not take account of the needs of those reusing the digital objects. Deposit Compliance and Initial Curation may be designed to support ReUse. Active Preservation will be designed to enable ReUse over time.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Specialist digital objects may only be reusable by a designated community with a specific knowledge base (e.g. in specific disciplines, research methods or context types). Sensitive data reuse may require approval for specific research types. Use may have to take place in a specific institution, country or secure environment.

AF09 Workflows

Processes and activities for managing, changing and maintaining digital objects and their associated data and metadata in line with legal, ethical, policy, and other standards and operating procedures (see AF23 "Legal & Ethical" and AF14 "Policy & Standards Management").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Standard operating procedures, workflow/business process diagrams and documentation related to how the repository approaches digital object management.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF10 Preservation

Monitoring both the technology landscape (see AF29 "Technical Infrastructure") and the user community (see AF20 "External Engagement") for any changes that could impact the usability or understanding (see AF08 "Reuse") of digital objects. When necessary, preservation actions are taken—such as migrating data formats, updating metadata (e.g., revising ontologies), or emulating the environment in which the digital object is used. These actions help ensure the long-term viability and continued accessibility of the digital object.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Preservation policies, strategies, plans and procedures that define how long artefacts will be preserved for, how potential preservation actions (emulation, file format updates, updates to semantic artefacts such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies) are approved and implemented. Preservation interacts with re-appraisal criteria set during Deposit & Appraisal, the changing Technical Infrastructure Landscape over time, and how the ReUse needs of the community are monitored.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: Active Preservation to ensure digital objects remain understandable and reusable for the long term is not provided by all repositories.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Specialist repositories need specific skills in data formats, research methodologies, metadata, and ontologies related to disciplines or content types. User characteristics influence community watch, object characteristics inform technology watch.

AF11 Provenance & Authenticity

Providing information about digital objects that details their history (provenance) and ensures their authenticity. Provenance and authenticity information can be captured at the point of deposit, generated during curation and preservation processes, and shared with data or metadata users.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Information about the creation, creators and history of the object requested at deposit. How the repository records information about changes to digital objects and what information is communicated externally (e.g. to end users).

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The level of repository provenance information will increase for changes made to digital objects during Initial Curation and Active Preservation.

Depositors, Users, Objects: The technical and semantic nature of the digital objects may influence how versions are specified and how changes are communicated.

AF12 Support

Providing guidance and responding to requests from depositors and users around deposit and appraisal, discovery, access and re-use of data and metadata.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Link to primary location where the repository provides supporting information or offers supporting services to depositors, users and others.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Support may be limited to a specific institution or country. Specialist repositories need specific skills in data formats, research methodologies, metadata, and ontologies related to disciplines or content types, to deliver relevant support.

Organisational Infrastructure

Organisational Infrastructure

AF13 Governance

The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the entity's mission is managed and executed.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Management and Decision documentation, organograms, management roles, role of host organisation, funders etc.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF14 Policy & Standards

The adoption and development of policies, standards and other criteria to guide practice, aligned with governance structures (see AF13 "Governance") and operational workflows (see AF09 "Workflows"), and in compliance with the applicable legal and ethical framework (see AF23 "Legal and Ethical").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Procedures for adopting and developing policies and standards, lists of policies and standards.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF15 Rights

The management of permissions, prohibitions, and obligations governing how digital objects are accessed and used by individuals and organisations, both within and outside the repository.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Rights Policy, Licences for deposit, access and reuse, non-compliance policy, sufficient rights to permit LoRCAP, rights related to succession plans.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF16 Resources

The organisational hierarchies and processes by which the organisational entity's human and financial resources are obtained and managed. This includes a knowledge of and an effective deployment of human, financial and energy assets.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Budget and finance strategies, plans, reports and projections.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF17 People & Expertise

The management of human resources to fulfil the mission. Includes ensuring that sufficient skills are available, internally or externally (see AF20 "External Engagement").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Skills Statement, Skills Development Plan, Staff Roles & Skills List

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Specialist repositories need specific skills in data formats, research methodologies, metadata, and ontologies related to disciplines or content types.

AF18 Third Party Dependencies

Identifying and managing third-party organisations, hosts, partners, and other actors that are essential to operations, including the delivery of data or metadata services.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Lists of partners, Partnership Statement, Partner Management Plan, Contracts/suppliers mapped to the functions and activities they provide for the organisation (e.g. a storage provider).

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF19 Continuity of Service

Ensuring business continuity by maintaining normal operations and preparing for disruptions. This includes non-technical processes (for technical, see AF29 "Technical Infrastructure") related to the organisation, digital object management (see AF09 "Workflows"), and security (see AF30 "Security"). It also covers recovery plans for events like service interruptions and disasters. Continuity includes succession planning for the end of a service.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

- Business Continuity Plan
- Disaster Recovery Plan
- Succession Plan

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

A business continuity incident could impact retention, deposit, curation or preservation. Succession plans may involve a change to the LoRCAP.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF20 External Engagement

Organisational interaction with external parties, including individuals, partner organisations, funders, and other relevant bodies.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Community Skills List, Community Engagement Plan, engagement with policy makers and funders, surveys of depositor and user needs

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF21 Release & Publishing

The processes by which the organisation creates, manages, approves, releases, updates and withdraws information artefacts(not deposited digital objects) such as publications, policies, guidelines, and other content related to the repository activities and functions. It includes publishing information that provides evidence for external assessments (see AF24 "Criteria, Assessment, Improvement") and supports external engagement (see AF20 "External Engagement").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Records management policy, records retention schedule, publication approval process

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: N/A

Depositors, Users, Objects: N/A

AF22 Interoperability

The protocols and processes by which people, processes, technologies and digital objects effectively interact with others, both within and across organisational entities.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Interoperability policy, plan, procedures. Links to and documentation of any machine accessible routes to data and/or metadata, e.g. APIs, OAI-PMH, aligned with Technical Infrastructure (see AF29 "Technical Infrastructure"). Crosswalks between relevant metadata standards and ontologies

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: N/A

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF23 Legal & Ethical

The legal and ethical obligations that the organisation must be aware of and adhere to.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Legal and/or ethical compliance statements, policies and procedures, ethical guidance lists, applicable legislation lists.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF24 Criteria, Assessment, Improvement

The processes used to assess compliance with standards, policies, and procedures, along with identifying actions for continuous and targeted improvement.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Change Management procedures, Self-Assessments, Certification

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF25 Analysis & Impact

The analysis of internal data and external information to verify and demonstrate that the organisation is effectively fulfilling its mission (see AF02 "Mission & Scope").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Business information analyses, identification and validation of external impact. Dashboards or interfaces for metrics and usage information.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

AF26 Training

Leveraging internal expertise to train data and metadata producers, owners, depositors, and users. Training can cover the entire digital object management lifecycle, from the conception of research to the reuse of data and metadata. It also includes training for internal staff, as well as for peer organisations, partners, and third parties.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Link to primary location where the organisation provides training materials and/or details of training programmes.

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: Training may be limited to a specific institution or country. Staff of specialist repositories need specific skills including data formats, research methodologies, metadata, and ontologies related to disciplines or content types, to deliver relevant training.

AF27 Research & Development (R&D)

Projects and other activities outside current operations, routine maintenance and upgrades. This can include new approaches to data, metadata, business processes, technology, security, and research infrastructure.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Documentation of project, specification, development and delivery processes. Links to information about projects the organisation is involved with. How products move from 'in development' to 'in production'

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

Technology

Technology

AF28 Storage & Integrity

The methods used to store and replicate digital objects' data and metadata, including the validation of replicated copies and the restoration of data from backups in case of errors.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Storage Documentation, integrity measures used, approach to integrity checking

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: maps to Retention

Depositors, Users, Objects: N/A

AF29 Technical Infrastructure

The comprehensive provision of hardware, software, and IT service management to support the organisation's entity. Monitoring the user community technical needs and broader technical landscape to update and maintain levels of technical service (see AF08 "ReUse").

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Technical Infrastructure Statement, Technical Infrastructure Plan, IT Service Management methodologies, 'Service Catalogues' (cf: FitSM¹²), repository-related software and source code

¹² FitSM: <https://www.fitsm.eu/>

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: The approach to the A|F will vary depending on the levels of retention, curation and preservation offered.

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

Security

Security

AF30 Security

Ensuring security across the organisation's infrastructure, digital object management, and systems. Security also extends to the boundary between the repository and external entities, including users, depositors and dependencies on third parties.

Suggestions for Transparent Information:

Information Security Statement, Information Security Plan, related certifications (e.g. ISO27001)

Variable Notes:

LoRCAP: N/A

Depositors, Users, Objects: characteristics inform A|F.

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¹³ <https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/>

¹⁴ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

¹⁵ <https://www.essex.ac.uk/about/faculty-of-social-sciences>

¹⁶ <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/en/>

¹⁷ <https://www.tuni.fi/en>

¹⁸ <https://www.gesis.org>

¹⁹ <https://www.sib.swiss/>

²⁰ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

²¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/hub>

²² <https://en.uit.no/>

²³ <https://csc.fi/en/>

²⁴ <https://www.dkrz.de/>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

A F	Activity or Function drawn from the reference list of Activities and Functions.
API	Application Programming Interface
CARE	Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics
CoreTrustSeal	CoreTrustSeal is an international, community based, non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures.
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud aims to provide researchers and innovators in Europe with an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment to publish, find and reuse data, tools and services.
FAIR	Principles designed to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
FitSM	FitSM is a free and lightweight standards family aimed at facilitating service management in IT service provision, including federated scenarios.
ISO27001	International standard for information security management
LoRCAP	Levels of retention, curation and preservation
N/A	Not Applicable
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PID	Persistent Identifier
SoP	Standard Operating Procedure
TRUST	Principles that define the characteristics of trustworthy digital repositories: Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology.
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

Appendix: Activities & Functions Diagram (large) with Key

- Dotted line: Strong connection
- Green Arrow: Flow to/from Actors
- Grey line: Support/Training Link

MaDSAF v2-